

The "Electron Transfer" Theory Applied to the Reactions in the (Photographic) Developing Bath.

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In a previous paper it was shown (Pandalai and Rao, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1933, 215, 23) that sodium sulphite besides acting as a preservative for developing solutions, preventing the atmospheric oxidation of the organic reducing agent, and also preventing yellow or brown stains on the negatives, also regenerates the oxidised developing agent enabling the latter to reduce more than its equivalent of the silver halide. The object of this paper is to show that the essential reactions occurring in the developing bath conform to typical reactions of "reduction" in the modern conception of the term, by an application of the "electron transfer" theory of oxidation-reduction processes. This theory regards the essential oxidation-reduction processes as a transfer of electrons from the reducer to the oxidiser. While it is convenient for describing the oxidation and reduction of ionised systems such as inorganic salts, *e.g.*,

it is less convenient for expressing the same *mutatis mutandis* of organic substances as their ionisations have to be taken into consideration. But our knowledge about the nature of these organic reducers in solution is still obscure and superficial. If we put (A) for the reducing agent and (B) for the substance reduced, typical reduction reactions may be expressed as

in which a gain of hydrogen atoms takes place; the reducer being the hydrogen donator and the reduced substance, the hydrogen acceptor.

In (ii) the anions of the reducer (A), reduce (B) by transferring to it the electron pair or the same as (B) gaining negative charges.

In (iii) the reducer (A) abstracts away a positive charge from the substance reduced (B), in other words (B) suffers a loss of positive charge.

These general ideas fit in, in a very significant manner to the reactions taking place during the development of a photographic plate, in other words, in the reduction of the silver halides by the organic reducing agents in presence of sodium sulphite. Most of the organic developing agents are substances containing hydrogen atoms which they can easily part with. These hydrogen atoms are in a large number of cases acidic in character. Thus hydroquinone for example ionises in solution :

In a few cases, however, they exhibit no acidic character and in such cases the theory in this form becomes somewhat artificial. The theory nevertheless has a very wide application.

The first reaction occurring in the developing bath is the ionisation in presence of alkali (accelerators) of the organic reducer (developer). Taking hydroquinone for example

the anions of the developer immediately lose their charges

In presence of sodium sulphite the primary oxidation product of the developer undergoes the following changes ultimately regenerating the original developer.

The quinonoid primary oxidation products being unstable in presence of hydroxyl ions, simultaneous reduction and substitution of hydroxyl in another molecule of quinone appears to take place. Referring to the transformation $\text{quinone} \rightleftharpoons \text{hydroquinone}$, Kehrmann (*Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 979) observed that "the lower the homologue and the more negative the substituents, the more easily quinones take up hydrogen and pass into hydroquinones." It is likely that in the method of Nietzki (*Ber.*, 1886, **19**, 1467) for preparing hydroquinone from quinone and sulphurous acid, the reactions occurring are those tabled above. Dodgson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 2435) has definitely shown that the course of the reaction is

Rzymkowski (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1925, **31**, 371) has used thiosulphate as a reducing agent in the determination of quinone (and quinhydrone) and the reactions here, are analogous to those taking place between quinone and sulphite ions.

The most important development reaction is the reduction of ionic into metallic silver. Tubandt (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, **110**, 196; 1921, **115**, 105) has studied the mechanism of transport of electricity through "solid electrolytic conductors" and has shown that in the halides of silver, the process of conductance is analogous to that in solutions. In the photographic plate the source of silver (being an emulsion of silver halide) the observation of Tubandt is very significant. Further, Hurter and Driffeld (E. Thorpe, "Dictionary of Applied Chemistry," 1924, Vol. 5, p. 208) have shown that when the reducer diffuses into the emulsion film and reaches the silver halide grains, the silver salt passes into solution and is ionised, reduction then occurring. Taking hydroquinone as a typical example the essential reactions are represented as below.

Reaction (a) involves the ionisation of the organic reducer in presence of a suitable medium giving rise to reactive hydrogen ions which are extremely powerful reducers. This reaction is also brought about by the well known oxidising action of silver halides on the organic developers. In reaction (b) part of development occurs, when the silver ions attain electroneutrality. Reactions (c) and (e) are typical hydrolytic oxidation-reduction reactions where sodium sulphite plays the most important part. It acts as a stain preventive preservative, and more important of both as hydrogen acceptor with a dual rôle, since in two hydrolytic oxidation-reduction reactions it regenerates the original developer (*vide e*) and reduces an amount of the silver ions (*vide e*) by abstracting away their positive charges. The silver formed in (b) and in (e) in solution, soon becomes saturated and equilibrium is attained. The organic developers function as hydrogen donators (*vide a*) and inductors (*vide e*) which is the secondary reaction and which is induced by the primary reaction namely the oxidation of the easily oxidisable substances such as hydroquinone, pyrogallol, metol, etc.

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Studies On Optical Activity and Chemical Constitution. Part I. Optically Active Bases and Acids.

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Phenylenebisiminocamphor (I) (Forster and Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 942), 1:4 naphthylenebisiminocamphor (II) (Singh and Singh, *ibid.*, 1920, 117, 1599), camphorylamino phenyliminocamphor (III) (Forster and Saville, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 789) and *pp'*s diphenylaminobisiminocamphor (IV) (Singh, Singh and Lal, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1971) are examples of substances possessing very high rotatory powers. All of them contain an optimum association of azethenoid groups, conjugated linkages and a benzene or a naphthalene ring within a narrow